

كتاب أخلاق المصطفى (The Character Traits of the Chosen One)

also known as "kitab akhlaq al-Mustafa"

By Jabir Musa, Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina state, Nigeria

Entry tags: Religious Group, Islamic Ethics and Moralities, Text, Hagiography, Islamic Traditions

Shiekh Abdullah ibn Fodio prepared the Book to describe the noble characters of Prophet Muhammad (SAW) within and outside his home, which are worthy of emulation to all Muslims based on the directives of Allah (SWT) in the Qur'an Q21:33. The book was made to present those characters that could upgrade the moral standard of the entire people to have acted on them such as piety, kindness, trustworthiness, charity, patience, etc.

Date Range: 1766 CE - 1828 CE

Region: Sokoto

Region tags: Africa, Western Africa, Benin, Burkina Faso, Niger, Togo, Nigeria, Chad, Cameroon

Sokoto around 1870, during the reign of Ahmadu Rufai. Adapted from AbdurRahman AbdulMoneim [https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Sokoto_Sultanate_\(cropped\).pr](https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Sokoto_Sultanate_(cropped).pr)

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: فوديو ع. (1828). كتاب أخلاق المصطفى. سكوتو.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://eap.bl.uk/archive-file/EAP535-1-4-2-10>

Notes: Kitab akhla-q al Mustafa by Sheikh Abdullahi bin Fodio [1244 A.H/1828 A.D]

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

– Source 1 URL: <https://siiasi.org/digital-archive/shaykh-abdullahi-ibn-fuduye/akhlaaq-l-mustafa/>

– Source 1 Description: Fuduye, A. (2016). The Character Traits of the Chosen One. Shareef, M. (trans). Institute of Islamic - African Studies International, Sankore.

General Variables

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

Notes: The textual copy of the book can be found at the national archives in Kaduna, Nigeria.

↳ Tomb

– No

Notes: The text was not stored in any tomb.

↳ Cemetery

– No

Notes: The text was not stored in a cemetery.

↳ Temple

– No

Notes: The text was not kept at a temple.

↳ Shrine

– No

Notes: The text was not stored in a shrine.

↳ Altar

– No

Notes: The text was not stored on the altar.

↳ Devotional marker

– No

Notes: The book was not reserved on a devotional marker.

↳ Cenotaph

– No

Notes: The book was not stored in a cenotaph.

↳ Church

– No

Notes: The text was not stored in a church.

- ↳ Mosque
 - Yes
 - Notes: Some copies of the book were kept in mosques for the benefit of people.
- ↳ Synagogue
 - No
 - Notes: The book was not stored in a synagogue.
- ↳ Triumphal Arch
 - No
 - Notes: The text was not placed on the triumphal arch.
- ↳ Monument
 - No
 - Notes: The text was not stored in a monument.
- ↳ Mass Gathering Point
 - No
 - Notes: The book was not reserved at the mass gathering point.
- ↳ Cave(s)
 - No
 - Notes: The text was not kept in caves.
- ↳ Hilltops
 - No
 - Notes: The text was not placed on hilltops.
- ↳ Other natural sanctuaries
 - No
 - Notes: The text was not stored in any natural sanctuaries.
- ↳ Boundary markers or lines
 - No
 - Notes: The text was not stored at boundary markers.
- ↳ Domestic contexts
 - Yes

Notes: Many copies could be found in domestic content for the personal uses of people.

↳ Library/archive

– Yes

Notes: Many copies were left within various archives after the uploaded manuscript was accessed at the National Archives Kaduna.

↳ Specify

–Specify: Markets and Bookshops.

Notes: Some copies of the book are available at markets and bookshops.

Methods of Composition

– Incised or Inscribed

Notes: The uploaded copy was a handwritten inscription on white paper.

↳ Method of inscription

–Other [specify]: Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

↳ Specify type of paper

–Specify: Brown

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Notes: The place was not accompanied by iconography.

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

–Other [specify]: No

Notes: The book was a direct copy of the original textbook without any modification or correction.

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Notes: No iconic image was kept near the text.

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Materiality

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Production & Intended Audience

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Yes

Notes: The polity supported the production of the text indirectly for the status of the Shiekh Abdullahi bn Fodio as the leader of the second action of the empire.

↳ Are the authors/copyists/engravers paid by the polity?

– No

Notes: But the copyists were highly encouraged by the polity.

↳ Does the polity provide financial support to religious infrastructure involved with textual production?

– No

Notes: The polity did not provide financial support for the reproduction of the text.

↳ Are the leaders of the polity and the religion the same figure?

– Yes

Notes: Leaders of the polity were among the religious figures of the empire.

↳ Are political officials involved in the support of textual production?

– Yes

Notes: Some political officials appeared among the copiest and taught people the content of the text.

↳ Are political officials and religious officials otherwise overlapping institutional networks?

– Yes

Notes: Members of the religious group support the other political officials on the religious directives in the manners of administration.

↳ Does the polity enforce religious observance according to text or texts?

– No

Notes: The polity did not mandate religious observance by the text.

↳ Is the polity legal code derived from religious text(s) in question?

– Yes

Notes: The text was among the guiding codes to the polity.

↳ Is preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax exemption) present in the polity to support the text(s)...

– No

Notes: The polity did not waive any tax to support the production of the text.

↳ Are religious specialists present/in charge of the production of the text or copies of the text?

– Yes

Notes: The production of the text happens to be among the tasks of religious professionals.

↳ Present full-time?

– No

Notes: They engaged in other activities in addition to the production of the text.

↳ Present part-time?

– Yes

Notes: The reproducers of the text engaged in other activities.

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific sex/gender?

– Yes

Notes: Religious specialists are mostly male by gender and have no restrictions on religious services.

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific ethnicity?

– No

Notes: Religious specialty is open to any ethnic group.

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific class/caste?

– No

Notes: The religious specialist is by knowledge.

↳ Are the religious specialists dedicated to the place for life?

– No

Notes: Religious specialists engaged in other activities apart from living in the palace.

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system?

– Yes

Notes: Some specialists were judges, some were appointed prayer leaders (Imams), and some were teachers.

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy?

– Yes

Notes: All the religious professionals have their place of sitting in the palace.

↳ Are there regulations/provisions for living spaces of religious specialists?

– No

Notes: Not necessarily.

↳ Are there regulations/provisions for training spaces of religious specialists?

– Yes

Notes: Every set of religious professionals has its distinct classes and separate curriculum.

↳ Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of a body of religious specialists?

– No

Notes: Religious professionals are only under the care of the caliphate.

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Total audience: 6000000

Notes: The audience spread across northern Nigeria, Niger, Gana, and the rest of the neighboring countries.

↳ Number of audience within the sample region (estimated population, numerical)

– Number: 6000000

↳ What is the size of the smallest known audience

– smallest audience: 2000000

↳ What is the size of the largest known audience

– largest audience: 4000000

↳ What factors might account for historical changes in audience size

– Specify: Birthrate, Deathrate, Migration etc.

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↳ Nature of audience

[select all that apply]

– Small religious group (seen as being part of a related larger religious group)

– Large official religious group with smaller religious groups also openly allowed

↳ Can scholarly and emic notions of the audience differ?

– No

Notes: The notions sound the same.

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Yes

Notes: New members are continuously invited to the religious group.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated according to the text?

– No

Notes: The text recommends proselytization.

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged according to the text?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

Notes: Religious professionals were encouraged to invite others to the religion.

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for all adherents?

– Yes

Notes: The text allowed all adherents to proselytize.

↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

Notes: The text encouraged missionary work for religious professionals.

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Notes: The text encourages all adherents to the missionary work.

↳ Are there specific rewards for proselytizing according to the text?

– No

Notes: The reward is not specified and shall be in the hereafter.

↳ Is proselytizing by coercion acceptable according to the text?

– No

Notes: The text rejects coercion in the proselytizing.

↳ Is textual justification for proselytizing part of the norm in the religious group?

– No

Notes: The text did not justify proselytizing.

↳ Is the text silent on matters of proselytization?

– No

Notes: The text hinted a little bit on the matter of proselytization.

↳ Is proselytizing forbidden or restricted by the text?

– No

Notes: The text did not forbid proselytization.

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Notes: The text was not considered scripture.

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Notes: The text was only written in Arabic language.

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Notes: The text did not mention the reformist movement.

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Notes: The text is not employed in ritual practices.

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Notes: There is no material significance attached to the text.

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Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Notes: The text did not make any distinction on a spirit-body.

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Notes: The text did not state supernatural monitoring.

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Ritual list

Notes: The text does include some manuals, rituals, and vocabularies.

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text was dedicated to socially approved norms.

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Notes: The text did not mention messianic belief.

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Notes: The text is not accompanied by any art design.

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Notes: The text was only written on the Prophet Muhammad's (SAW) ethics.

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Notes: The text did not indicate a belief system, but most relevant books pointed to the system in the principles of the Shari'ah.

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Notes: The text did not extend discussion on eschatology.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– I don't know

Notes: Supernatural punishment is not mentioned in the text.

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Notes: There is an Arabic and English-translated version of the text.

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

Notes: Both versions are viewed as valid.

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– No

Notes: The variation might not be except in the number of pages and style of writing while copying the text.

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Notes: Both versions are considered proper.

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– Yes

Notes: The text expressed legal codes on the expected behavior of Muslims.

↳ Are there formal institutions merged with the state or polity of the religious group?

– No

Notes: However, the ethics described by the text are expected to be applied by the entire Muslim world.

↳ Does the text express authority of ethical guidelines? (E.g.: adat literature that dictates or records "customary practices")

– Yes

Notes: The text discusses the ethics of Muslim life.

↳ Life cycle rituals?

– No

↳ Everyday rituals?

– Yes

Notes: The text does express some worship functions.

↳ Does the code apply to gender specific contexts?

– No

Notes: The text is applied to the entire sexes.

↳ Other behavioral guidelines?

– Yes

Notes: The text guide on the better manner of social interaction.

↳ Are there non-institutionalized "acceptable" social punishments specified?

– No

Notes: The text did not mention any act of social punishment.

↳ Are there non-institutionalized "acceptable" social rewards specified?

– No

Notes: The text did not express any non-approved social reward.

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Notes: Reincarnation is not accepted in the religion of the text.

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

Notes: The text is a single book.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Notes: Supernatural reward is not mentioned in the text.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

Notes: The text encourages trustworthiness.

↳ Courage (in battle)

– Yes

↳ Courage (generic)

– Yes

Notes: The text strongly advocated courage.

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– Yes

↳ Generosity/charity

– Yes

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– Yes

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– Yes

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– Yes

↳ Cooperation

– Yes

Notes: The text called for unity and cooperation.

- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
 - Yes
- ↳ Moderation/frugality
 - Yes
 - Notes: The text rejected the habit of frugality.
- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
 - Yes
- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
 - Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
 - Yes
- ↳ Strength (physical)
 - Yes
- ↳ Power/status/nobility
 - Yes
- ↳ Humility/modesty
 - Yes
- ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
 - Yes
- ↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
 - Yes
- ↳ Optimism/hope
 - Yes
- ↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
 - Yes

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– Yes

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– Yes

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– Yes

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– Yes

↳ Other important virtues

– Yes

Does the text require fasting?

– I don't know

Notes: The text directed the practice of fasting in the month of Ramadan.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

Notes: The text is part of the literature on the biography of the Prophet Muhammad (SAW).

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

Notes: The culture is expected to be emulated by every Muslim.

↳ Behavioral literature?

– Yes

Notes: The text described the behavior of the Prophet Muhammad (SAW).

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Moral ethics.

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– Yes

Notes: The text was designed on the Hijrah lunar calendar.

↳ What is the arrangement of the calendar? [Select all that apply]

– Lunar?

Notes: The text was restricted to the Lunar calendar.

↳ Does the calendar specifically dictate acceptable times for certain activities?

– Yes

Notes: The calendar dictated the time for the annual fasting and Eid celebrations.

↳ Planting?

– No

↳ Water management? (such as opening or closing dams/dykes)

– No

↳ Harvest?

– No

↳ Naming ceremonies (for toddlers)?

– Yes

Notes: The naming ceremony is done on the seventh day after the birth.

↳ "First haircuts" (pre-teen)

– Yes

Notes: The first haircut is done on the seventh day of the birth.

↳ Ceremonies marking puberty/entry into adulthood?

– No

↳ Marriage?

– No

Notes: The calendar did not precisely point to a particular month of a marriage ceremony.

↳ House construction (often a metaphor for marriage)?

– No

Notes: The calendar did not indicate an exact period of house construction.

↳ Divorce?

– No

↳ Warfare?

– No

↳ Funerary services?

– No

Notes: Funerary activities are done at the death of a deceased person.

↳ Trade/commerce?

– No

Notes: Trade and commerce are done at personal convenience.

↳ Festivals?

– Yes

Notes: The calendar dictates the period of Eid festivals.

↳ Frequency of festivals?

– Specify: periodical

Notes: The festivals are done at the beginning of the month of shawal and the tenth day of the month of Zul-Hajj.

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s)?

– All members

Notes: All members are expected to attend the festivals.

↳ On average, how many participants are gathered at festivals?

– number: Depends on the audience

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s)?

– Yes

↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population?

– No

↳ Pilgrimages?

– Yes

Notes: Pilgrimage is done in the month of Zul-Hjj.

↳ How strict are the stipulations regarding pilgrimage?

– obligatory for some

Notes: The pilgrimage is obligatory for those who are opportune to attend.

↳ Is encouraging pilgrimages a primary reason for the existence of the text?

– No

Notes: The primary reason for the text is to describe the ethics of the Prophet Muhammad (SAW).

↳ Are pilgrimages guided by the text associated with particular life events?

– No

↳ Does pilgrimage guided by this text involve/follow major routes/roads?

– Yes

Notes: The pilgrimage is done at particular places in Arabia.

↳ Is the maintenance of the routes guided by the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the pilgrimage conducted by walking or by other means?

– No

Notes: Pilgrimages can be conducted by any means

↳ Feasting?

– No

Notes: The text did not guide on the ethics of feasting.

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Notes: Co-sacrifice is prohibited in Islam.

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

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Notes: Islam did not approve the burial of corpses with goods.

Are formal burials present in the text?

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Notes: The text did not extend discussion on burial.

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

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Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– No

Notes: The text did not mention supernatural beings.

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Notes: The human spirit was not quoted in the text.

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

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Notes: The text restricted discussion on the characters of the Prophet Muhammad (SAW).

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

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– Yes

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–Other [specify]: The text discussed mainly the outstanding characters of the prophet (S.A.W)

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

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Does the text guide divination practices?

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Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

Notes: The text hinted at some ritual services of the Prophet (SAW).

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances?

– Hours: 2

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Notes: The text requires attendance of weekly Friday congregations.

↳ On average, how many participants gather in one location?

– Number of participants: 700

↳ Interval of time between performances (in hours)

– Hours: 168

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– No

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices?

– Yes

↳ Is there use of intoxicants?

– No

Notes: Intoxicants are entirely prohibited in Islam.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Notes: The text is not accompanied by any art design.

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Notes: There is an Arabic and English-translated version of the text.

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

Notes: Both versions are viewed as valid.

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– No

Notes: The variation might not be except in the number of pages and style of writing while copying the text.

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Notes: Both versions are considered proper.

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

Notes: The text is a single book.

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

Notes: The text is part of the literature on the biography of the Prophet Muhammad (SAW).

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

Notes: The culture is expected to be emulated by every Muslim.

↳ Behavioral literature?

– Yes

Notes: The text described the behavior of the Prophet Muhammad (SAW).

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Moral ethics.

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Ritual list

Notes: The text does include some manuals, rituals, and vocabularies.

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Notes: The text was only written on the Prophet Muhammad's (SAW) ethics.

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– Yes

Notes: The text expressed legal codes on the expected behavior of Muslims.

↳ Are there formal institutions merged with the state or polity of the religious group?

– No

Notes: However, the ethics described by the text are expected to be applied by the entire Muslim world.

↳ Does the text express authority of ethical guidelines? (E.g.: adat literature that dictates or records "customary practices")

– Yes

Notes: The text discusses the ethics of Muslim life.

↳ Life cycle rituals?

– No

↳ Everyday rituals?

– Yes

Notes: The text does express some worship functions.

↳ Does the code apply to gender specific contexts?

– No

Notes: The text is applied to the entire sexes.

↳ Other behavioral guidelines?

– Yes

Notes: The text guide on the better manner of social interaction.

↳ Are there non-institutionalized "acceptable" social punishments specified?

– No

Notes: The text did not mention any act of social punishment.

↳ Are there non-institutionalized "acceptable" social rewards specified?

– No

Notes: The text did not express any non-approved social reward.

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– Yes

Notes: The text was designed on the Hijrah lunar calendar.

↳ What is the arrangement of the calendar? [Select all that apply]

– Lunar?

Notes: The text was restricted to the Lunar calendar.

↳ Does the calendar specifically dictate acceptable times for certain activities?

– Yes

Notes: The calendar dictated the time for the annual fasting and Eid celebrations.

↳ Planting?

– No

↳ Water management? (such as opening or closing dams/dykes)

– No

↳ Harvest?

– No

↳ Naming ceremonies (for toddlers)?

– Yes

Notes: The naming ceremony is done on the seventh day after the birth.

↳ "First haircuts" (pre-teen)

– Yes

Notes: The first haircut is done on the seventh day of the birth.

↳ Ceremonies marking puberty/entry into adulthood?

– No

↳ Marriage?

– No

Notes: The calendar did not precisely point to a particular month of a marriage ceremony.

↳ House construction (often a metaphor for marriage)?

– No

Notes: The calendar did not indicate an exact period of house construction.

↳ Divorce?

– No

↳ Warfare?

– No

↳ Funerary services?

– No

Notes: Funerary activities are done at the death of a deceased person.

↳ Trade/commerce?

– No

Notes: Trade and commerce are done at personal convenience.

↳ Festivals?

– Yes

Notes: The calendar dictates the period of Eid festivals.

↳ Frequency of festivals?

– Specify: periodical

Notes: The festivals are done at the beginning of the month of shawal and the tenth day of the month of Zul-Hajj.

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s)?

– All members

Notes: All members are expected to attend the festivals.

↳ On average, how many participants are gathered at festivals?

– number: Depends on the audience

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s)?

– Yes

↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population?

– No

↳ Pilgramages?

– Yes

Notes: Pilgrimage is done in the month of Zul-Hjj.

↳ How strict are the stipulations regarding pilgrimage?

– obligatory for some

Notes: The pilgrimage is obligatory for those who are opportune to attend.

↳ Is encouraging pilgrimages a primary reason for the existence of the text?

– No

Notes: The primary reason for the text is to describe the ethics of the Prophet Muhammad (SAW).

↳ Are pilgrimages guided by the text associated with particular life events?

– No

↳ Does pigrimage guided by this text involve/follow major routes/roads?

– Yes

Notes: The pilgrimage is done at particular places in Arabia.

↳ Is the maintenance of the routes guided by the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the pilgrimage conducted by walking or by other means?

– No

Notes: Pilgrimages can be conducted by any means

↳ Feasting?

– No

Notes: The text did not guide on the ethics of feasting.

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Notes: The text did not make any distinction on a spirit-body.

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Notes: The text did not indicate a belief system, but most relevant books pointed to the system in the principles of the Shari'ah.

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Notes: Reincarnation is not accepted in the religion of the text.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

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Notes: Co-sacrifice is prohibited in Islam.

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Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: The text discussed mainly the outstanding characters of the prophet (S.A.W)

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Notes: The text did not state supernatural monitoring.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– I don't know

Notes: Supernatural punishment is not mentioned in the text.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Notes: Supernatural reward is not mentioned in the text.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Notes: The text did not mention messianic belief.

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Notes: The text did not extend discussion on eschatology.

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text was dedicated to socially approved norms.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

Notes: The text encourages trustworthiness.

↳ Courage (in battle)

– Yes

↳ Courage (generic)

– Yes

Notes: The text strongly advocated courage.

- ↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence
– Yes
- ↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance
– Yes
- ↳ Generosity/charity
– Yes
- ↳ Selflessness/selfless giving
– Yes
- ↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude
– Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity
– Yes
- ↳ Respectfulness/courtesy
– Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience/filial piety
– Yes
- ↳ Fidelity/loyalty
– Yes
- ↳ Cooperation
– Yes
Notes: The text called for unity and cooperation.
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
– Yes
- ↳ Moderation/frugality
– Yes

Notes: The text rejected the habit of frugality.

- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
– Yes
- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
– Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
– Yes
- ↳ Strength (physical)
– Yes
- ↳ Power/status/nobility
– Yes
- ↳ Humility/modesty
– Yes
- ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
– Yes
- ↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
– Yes
- ↳ Optimism/hope
– Yes
- ↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
– Yes
- ↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
– Yes
- ↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
– Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– Yes

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– Yes

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– Yes

↳ Other important virtues

– Yes

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– I don't know

Notes: The text directed the practice of fasting in the month of Ramadan.

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

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– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

Notes: The text described the manners of the Prophet (SAW) while extending the religion of Allah through the Islamic war (Jihad).

↳ Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?
– No

↳ Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?
– No

↳ Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?
– No

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:
– An empire

Does the text specify forms of taxation?
– No

Notes: The text did not specify forms of taxation.

Does the text detail interaction with public works?
– Yes

Notes: The text described how the prophet (SAW) interacted with the public for the emulation of the people.

↳ Does the text advocate for public food storage?
– No

Notes: The text did not advocate for public food storage for its restriction on the traits of the prophet (SAW) alone.

↳ Does the text provide guidance for food distribution?
– No

Notes: The text did not give any guidance on food distribution to the people.

↳ Does the text regulate places for civic functions?
– Yes

Notes: The text restricted civic function to the exemplary life set by the prophet (SAW).

↳ Does the text regulate places for the practice of justice?

– Yes

Notes: The text directs people to render justice in all places of social interaction.

↳ Does the text advocate or specify controls for water management (irrigation, flood control)?

– No

Notes: The text did not make provision for the water management.

↳ Does the text specify restrictions on common transportation?

– No

Notes: The text did not specify restrictions on common transportation.

↳ Other form of regulation of public works?

–Specify: Transaction

Notes: The text guided the application of justice while transacting with people.

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Notes: The caliphate established educational institutions to impart religious knowledge to the book and the rest of its likes.

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– An empire

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Notes: However, the available institutions set the book within the content of its curricula.

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– Yes

Notes: The text encouraged people to search for wisdom to enhance their life standards.

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Notes: The book left education accessible to the general public.

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Notes: The text did not restrict education to the professionals alone.

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Notes: The book provides education to both sexes.

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Notes: The text and the rest of its likes did not restrict education to one gender but rather, unrestricted public.

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Notes: The text did not make specifications on teaching relationships.

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Notes: The text considered teachers as a source of knowledge to the people.

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

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Society & Institutions

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